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Research Article

PREVALANCE OF MALNUTRITION AMON ADOLESCENT GIRLS: A STUDY OF GIRLS COLLEGE LAHORE

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Abstract:

Less intake of off taking by girls is very harmful because as we know that girls in future need good health to give birth to young ones. If their diet will not good their all work activities will be poor and will stop responding properly about their studies .They will not be able to give proper attention toward their studies. This lack of food or malnutrition is seen most in those girls who are school or college going. Where they spend whole day and they did not take plenty of food to increase level of nutrients in their body. So to check out the overall ratio we make a study report about this going condition of malnutrition. We visit them and ask different questions about their diet which they take in whole day .And in this period of time which type of food they take and how much. We take 145-150 respondents When we get answers and we make report it was concluded that the results we have seen was mainly the income of that family, if her mother father both are doing jobs or his father is doing a good job or business their intake of food will be healthy but if they have lack of food they will show malnutrition. Another thing which we have seen in this report after asking question was about the education of mothers. Either mother was educated or not. Because if mother will be educated she will take care of their children n and will have knowledge about nutrients level. By checking their weight we see different results with different ratios.

Key Words: *Educated mothers, Lack of nutrition, Lack of knowledge about food, income.*

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INTRODUCTION:

We visit colleges and schools to check the correct level of malnutrition in girls who are teenagers [1]. In this stage of life, height and a lot of body changes occur in human body especially in girls. Actually malnutrition is defined as the level of food which we are taking, with how much consistency play important role [2]. A lot of girls did not get proper diet in their daily routine or if they are taking diet, then it will not be healthy or full of nutrition so instead of giving them good health this imbalance diet will disturb their nutritional level [3]. If diet will not good then height of girls will not increase with the passage of time and they will become less heighted and weak [4]. Usually most of people do not take proper balance of diet as by taking fruits, meat, nuts, vegetables which include proteins vitamins etc which help our body to increase level of nutrition in body [5]. By taking proper food we can increase our height and weight in teenage which we also called as the period of growth of the body [6]. But if girls will not take proper diet or going to their schools or colleges without taking breakfast and not taking good food in whole day, they will feel hunger and will have proper nutritional level in their body which will create a lot of problems [7]. We take survey to check ratio of health girls as compared to those who are not taking proper and healthy food. By asking questions about food they are taking we get different results where we see different ratios about level of food they take, how much food they take in whole day. Their family income is good or normal. Either they are able to get good intake if food or just they are fulfilling their hunger [8]. By taking less fruits ,meat or we can say that by taking less healthy food, a lot of deficiencies occur in human body as lack of iron, vitamins etc which cause serious problems in future [9]. Not taking good food with full of nutrition cause serious issue as when girls in future taking birth to their babies, chances will increase more as their babies will less weight or will not healthy as other babies at the time of birth [10]. We make this report to check the overall ratio of nutrition in bodies and then aware them to take good intake of food for their good future.

METHODOLOGY:

We make this study to check out the percentage of malnutrition in girls who are living and doing their study in colleges of Lahore. So we took a survey and make report about the level of malnutrition we have examine in girls by asking questions and by taking survey. After this we make report, we take about 145-150 respondents from those we ask questions and take survey. After asking different questions and get their answers we collect whole data and analyze it to make a proper report on it. We check out the percentage of food girls was taking in whole day and quality of food which they were taking. After collection of data from girls who was teenagers, we move it from different stages as we first check out the positive and negative response of respondents. After this we take our percentage of each question and they analyze the whole results. After completion of procedure and final analysis we make this report about malnutrition in girls. We also check out their weights and make different graphs for those who were underweight, normal weight or were having over- weight.

RESULTS:

By taking this survey and by making report we conclude that some of them was normal weight as about 18-20% girls were with normal weight. But about 45-46% was under-weight and 24-25% was over-weight. We also check that what the minimum and maximum weight of these girls was so we see that less weight was about 20-22 kg and maximum was 68-70 kg. We also concluded that the diet of girls also get affected with their mother's education. If mother will be educated and will have how know about their diet then they can give good source of food to their children. Another important point which we have seen in this report is source of income, if there will be good source of income then girls will take good food and become health but if there will be less income where father is running whole family then children cannot take proper diet they will just fulfill their hunger and will show less nutritional level.

In this graph we see the weight of girls as how many of them was under-weight, normal weight and over-weighted.

Fig: 01

Table: 01 Frequency of food intake.

Food	Once a week	2-4 Per week	5-6 Per week	Once a day	2-3 Per day	4-5 Per day	Never
Beef, Chicken, Fish	45%	20%	9%	12%	4%	-	90%
Fruit	26%	12%	9%	41%	9%	3%	-
Vegetable	12%	5%	17%	50%	12%	3%	-
Dairy Products	13%	5%	4%	64%	10%	2%	-
Beverages(tea or juices)	17%	8%	8%	38%	14%	2%	13%
Supplements	12%	8%	3%	17%	1%	-	59%

Table shows the percentage of food which they take in their daily and weekly diet with how much consistency. As in the form of meat, milk, fruits and other supplements.

Fig: 02

Table: 2 Association between BMI and Mother's Education

Mother's Education	BMI	Underweight (<19kg/m ²)	Normal (19.0-24.9 kg/m ²)	Overweight (25-29.9kg/m ²)	Obese (>30 kg/m ²)	Total
	Illiterate	14	10	6	0	30
	Primary	5	2	1	0	8
	Middle	3	4	5	0	12
	Metric	13	5	7	3	28
	FA/F.Sc	7	4	3	3	17
	Graduate	10	2	10	1	23
	Master	8	2	2	0	12
Chi-Square: 16.030		DF: 4		SL: 003		

Table: 3 24 Hour Recall

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean \pm SD	Recommended Value
Energy	110	993	587 \pm 258	1900 Kcal ¹
Calcium	104	990	609.6 \pm 235	1000mg ²
Magnesium	72	410	173 \pm 48	310mg ³
Protein	10	70	29 \pm 11	48g ⁴
Fat	10	91	42 \pm 21	77g ⁵

DISCUSSION:

In this survey we also check the weight of girls and compare their weight as with age to those girls who are living in other countries [11]. We perform different practicals to assess the actual and beneficial weight of girls which complete their nutritional value. Every female either she is in called as women or girl should take care of her diet and nutrition level to check out the weight of their body and make themselves healthy and strong [12]. Because by taking less nutritional diet girls will feel low and their energy level will start decreasing. We check it out that about 35-38 women from every 100 are suffering from malnutrition in Pakistan because of less intake of good food and having less knowledge [13]. If girls will not take proper diet then as with the passage of time when their age will increase their problems will also increase and at that time to fulfill the nutritional value in body will be more difficult. We should spread awareness about proper intake of nutrients by girls is very effective for their future life [14].

CONCLUSION:

So with whole this study we conclude that proper intake of food is necessary. But there are some other major affects occur which cause malnutrition as less knowledge about intake of proper food ,family income and education of mother affects a lot. When family will be well established and will have enough money to fulfill all requirements then children will be healthy and will have complete nutrients level in their bodies.

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